

SPEECH DISORDERS ARE NOT A DISEASE

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Annotation

This article talks about speech impairment. Speech is not a disease, it is not conductive uttered sounds.

Keywords

Dyslalia, dysarthria, rhinolalia, alalia, aphasia, correction, sound.

Speech impairment is not a disease. As everyone knows, every child has its own character. This character is manifested in each child in his own way. Parents try to overcome the character of their child in their own way. That is, he brings up as best he can.

Psychologists say that every child has his own psychological approach. This approach is different for every child. Preschool children love to play the most. Games develop children. The development of children looks like speech of the expressive and impressive side. The child says he wants to give information about himself. What did he see today, what did he hear today. And this information should be processed with the help of adults. That is why parents and other scary people should listen to the child.

Each child develops in their own way. Some children develop speech quickly, while others develop speech slowly. The development of speech is conditioned by social life. In social life, the child tries to give an idea about his life.

With the help of speech, the child tries to give an understanding of his thoughts. Speech disorders are sounds that are hard to pronounce. Speech disorders include dyslalia, dysarthria, rhinolalia, alalia, aphasia.

Dyslalia is a violation of sound pronunciation in children with normal hearing and intact innervation of the articulatory apparatus. With dyslalia, there may be a violation and difficulty in pronouncing any phonemes in the child's native language.

Reasons for dysplasia:

- shortened frenulum of the tongue (hyoid ligament);
- defects in the structure of the jaws;
- incorrect structure of the palate;
- thick lips;

- improper upbringing of the child's speech in the family;
- imitation;
- bilingualism in the family;
- pedagogical neglect;
- underdevelopment of phonemic hearing.

Dyslalia can be caused by the child's inability to keep the tongue in the right position or quickly move from one movement to another.

Dysarthria is a speech disorder caused by diseases of the nervous system or a disorder in the work of the vocal cords, facial and respiratory muscles.

Localization of the pathological process, leading to dysarthria in children, can develop at different levels of the nervous system responsible for the formation of sounds, the logical harmony of the story:

- the nuclei of the cranial nerves responsible for the nervous control of the tongue, lips, soft palate, etc.;
- pathways between the cortex and cerebral nuclei;
- subcortical centers;
- cerebellum and pathways, conduction pathways from it and to it;
- cortex.

Diagnosis is carried out simultaneously by a neurologist (finds out the level of topical damage to the nervous system and the nature of the pathological process) and a speech therapist (determines the degree of speech disorders in order to make a correction prognosis).

Treatment is aimed at eliminating or stabilizing the background pathology that led to speech disorders, as well as articulation correction.

Rhinolalia is a speech disorder that manifests itself as a pronounced distortion of speech and incorrect pronunciation of individual sounds. As a rule, the development of this speech pathology is caused by an incorrect structure of the speech apparatus. Rhinolalia is a defect in sound pronunciation and timbre of the voice, due to anatomical and physiological disorders of the speech apparatus.

Rhinolalia in manifestation differs from dyslalia in the presence of an altered timbre of the voice. With this disease, phonation and articulation of sounds differ significantly from the norm.

With normal phonation, in the process of pronouncing speech sounds (with the exception of nasal ones), the nasal and nasopharyngeal cavities are separated from the oral and pharyngeal cavities. These areas are separated by palatopharyngeal closure, which is carried out by contraction of the muscles of the palate, posterior and lateral walls of the pharynx.

Along with the movement of the palate during phonation, the posterior pharyngeal wall thickens, which contributes to the contact of the soft palate and the posterior pharyngeal wall. The soft palate during speech constantly rises and falls to different heights depending on the speed of speech and the spoken words or sounds. This force is greater for vowels than for consonants. The weakest closing occurs with the pronunciation of "B", and the strongest - with "C" (as a rule, several times stronger than with the vowel "A"). Depending on the type of dysfunction of the palatine and pharyngeal closure, different forms and manifestations of rhinolalia are distinguished.

Alalia is an underdevelopment of speech, or its complete absence, in which the child understands everything perfectly and hears clearly.

As a rule, with alalia, the child cannot speak correctly due to a limited vocabulary, or incorrect construction of a phrase. In the most complex form of the disease, speech is completely absent. In the mildest form, the symptoms of the disease are similar to those of underdeveloped speech.

It is worth focusing on the fact that the mental development of the child is in accordance with age. But social pressure can aggravate the situation: peers, relatives. This problem should be solved as early as possible, otherwise, in the future, there may be problems with the socialization and self-staging of the child in society.

Multiple factors can influence the onset and development of the disease, which are usually divided into intrauterine and external. As practice shows, alalia occurs when several reasons are combined at once.

Intrauterine include an unsuccessful abortion, the threat of miscarriage, excessive use of drugs by the mother, complicated toxicosis, bad habits, falls on the stomach, difficult childbirth, during which the child was injured, mother's illness during pregnancy.

The external causes of the formation of alalia in children under three years of age include encephalitis, bilateral pneumonia, acute respiratory viral infections, rickets, meningitis, as well as traumatic brain injuries, anesthesia during surgery, and insufficient attention of parents to the speech development of the child.

Aphasia is an acquired speech disorder that can occur after brain damage (stroke, head injury, tumors or inflammation in the brain). As a result of aphasia, all language abilities are affected: to speak, understand, read, write.

Most often, aphasia occurs as a result of strokes: ischemic and hemorrhagic (most often with a mixed and total form). Also, the causes of aphasia disorder can be:

- brain tumors;
- trepanation of the skull and other interventions in the cranium;
- encephalitis and other inflammatory processes of the brain;
- progressive diseases of the central nervous system;
- different kinds of cranial injuries.

Each of these speech disorders has its own correctional and pedagogical work. Corrective - speech therapy work is manifested with the help of interventions of a speech therapist.

Speech disorders are not a disease. But for each speech disorder has a pedagogical approach. Speech therapy work is carried out by methods, principles and various diagnostics. With the help of medicine, a speech therapist works with children with alalia, aphasia, and dysarthria. These speech disorders are caused by pedagogy and medicine. But speech disorders are not diseases. Each violation of speech speech therapy work is carried out orally, visual aids. And it gives good results.

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